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THE METAVERSE IN EDUCATION: POSSIBILITIES AND CHALLENGES TODAY

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, it has been possible to observe a major technological revolution. The COVID-19 pandemic has made information around the world even more accessible in the palm of our hands, a reality never seen before in history. The educational process has moved from blackboard and paper to online, signaling that a new reality would enter without revival. Talking about the Metaverse in Education not only instigates interest among some people in this subject, but can also point to possibilities and challenges for its implementation in the teaching and learning process.